

Selecting Feature Representation for Online Summarisation of Egocentric Videos

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Problem

One important aspect of the video summarisation pipeline is the extraction of features from the video frames. For an online application, two factors must be considered when choosing a descriptor: (1) the ability of the chosen feature space to identify the meaningful attributes of the scene; (2) the computational cost of processing (the extraction process, and algorithm running time associated with the feature dimensionality).

We are looking to choose the most suitable feature space for creating online keyframe summary from a streaming egocentric video.

Experiments

- (1) Compare the processing time to extract the different features for the toy video. For each descriptor, we calculated the average time of extraction by repeating the process 20 times.
- (2) Compare the qualities of the summaries based on the different feature spaces.
- (3) An example of keyframe summaries obtained by all 7 features and their matched frames with the ground truth, for ADL dataset video #16.

(1) – Extraction Time

Descriptor	Size		Visual Information			Time(sec)	Dimensions
	resized	original	colour	scene	deep learning		
RGB moments (RGB)		✓	✓			50	54
HSV histogram [32 4 2] (HSV)	✓	✓	✓			30	256
CENTRIST		✓		✓		160	254
Gist	✓			✓		232	512
Color Layout MPEG7 (CL)		✓	✓			519	192
places205-AlexNet CNN (SF205)		✓		✓	✓	494	4096
VGG CNN (VGG)		✓			✓	2377	4096

(2) – Performance

(3) – Results

	1- brushing teeth	2- combing/ looking at the mirror	3- pouring water /drink	4- washing dishes	5- making tea/ coffee	6- looking into the fridge	7- eating /drink	8- making hot /cold food	9- vacuuming	10- washing dishes	11- watching TV	12- adjusting thermosta t	13- laundry
Ground Truth													
a) HSV													
b) RGB													
c) CL													
d) CENTRIST													
e) Gist													
f) SF205													
g) VGG													